

Low Complexity Dynamic Obstacle Detection for Intelligent Road Infrastructure

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Abstract—We present a new lightweight algorithm for detecting the points related to dynamic obstacles within LIDAR point clouds. Thanks to its low complexity, the algorithm can be used either to enable near-sensor embedded functionalities or to enhance the capabilities of intelligent infrastructure in the C-ITS context. Experimental results on the real-world TUMTraF Intersection Dataset show that the proposed approach can run in real-time on an ARM Cortex A9 CPU while still reaching a detection precision of 69.1%, which is consistent with state of the art performance of deep neural network-based approaches.

Index Terms—LIDAR, dynamic obstacle detection, Intelligent Transportation Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Intelligent, connected road infrastructure plays a central role in the deployment of Cooperative Intelligent Transportation Systems (C-ITS). Intelligent road infrastructure participates in the analysis of traffic situations and supports connected vehicles and other traffic participants in making the right decisions to improve road safety. An essential task of this traffic situation analysis pipeline concerns the detection of dynamic objects.

Multiple sensor technologies have been investigated for this task. While radars can exploit the Doppler effect to detect moving objects, LIDAR (Light Detection And Ranging) sensors have the advantage of providing 3D Point Clouds (PCs) with much higher density and angular precision, which is beneficial in dense urban traffic situations. While cameras can provide high classification accuracy, their limited 3D localisation capability affects their use in this task.

Several methods for detecting dynamic obstacles from LIDAR PCs have been investigated in the research community during the last decade. Existing methods can be grouped into three categories depending of their outputs. The first category consists in a binary segmentation of each individual point of a LIDAR PC as dynamic or static [1]–[3]. Methods in the second category transform first the PC into an intermediate 2D Bird-Eye-View (BEV) grid-based representation, such as an Occupancy Grid composed of multiple adjacent cells, and estimate the movement of each cell by applying methods based on particle filters [4]–[10]. The third category includes methods that perform PC-to-object detection and whose outputs include the 3D bounding boxes of dynamic objects [11]–[13].

Approaches that reach interesting accuracy levels within the first and the third categories are based on deep neural networks which require high performance GPUs consuming up to hundreds of Watts of power to run in real-time. On the other hand, grid-based approaches are less energy intensive but, to meet real-time constraints, existing approaches still need GPUs whose power consumption can reach up to 10 times the power consumption of the LIDAR device. The objective of the present work is to propose a low complexity algorithm for the detection of dynamic obstacles from LIDAR PCs. We do so for two reasons: Firstly, to enable ‘smart LIDARs’, meaning a LIDAR sensor accompanied by a near-sensor, low-power and resource-constrained computing hardware that enhances the sensor’s capabilities. Secondly, to enable resource constrained (such as solar powered) Intelligent Road Infrastructure such as multi-sensor Road Side Units (RSU). This equipment typically embarks one or more smart cameras that perform object detection and classification. The association of these cameras with a range sensor both compensates each type of sensor’s limitations (e.g., dependence on lighting conditions for cameras, lower classification capability for range sensors) and improves the precision of speed estimates for moving objects. The multi-sensor association finally also enables new functionalities such as RSU malfunction detection, due to technical failure or malicious intervention.

In this paper, we present a new lightweight approach that enables to distinguish at a low computational cost the points of a LIDAR PC that correspond to moving obstacles, from the points that belong to static objects or to the ground. The approach is specifically designed for applications where the LIDAR device is mounted on a static support. The approach is evaluated using the R2 release of the publicly available TUMTraF Intersection Dataset [14] which include data from a LIDAR monitoring the traffic on a busy intersection. Experimental results show that the proposed approach can run in real-time on an embedded ARM CPU without requiring a GPU, while still reaching a precision of detection of 69.1%, which is consistent with state of the art performance of deep neural network-based approaches which all require high performance GPUs to run in real-time.

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

A LIDAR device produces a PC at each iteration t . The PC is composed of both ground and non-ground points [15]. Ground points correspond to the ground or road surface de-

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Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed method. (a): 3D LIDAR PC, with manually annotated clusters only for explanation purpose. Cluster A is a static object, B is a dynamic one, cluster C is the ground. F1: computation of inconsistent points. (b): inconsistent points (green). F2: ground extraction. (c): non-ground inconsistent points (red). F3: projection on a 2D BEV grid. (d): Inconsistency Grid (IG) with inconsistent cells in red. F4: dynamic cell estimation. (e): Dynamic Grid (DG) with dynamic cells in blue. F5: dynamic points extraction. (f): dynamic points (blue)

tected by the LIDAR. Non-ground points are LIDAR measurements related to obstacles. In a traffic scenario, obstacles can be cars, pedestrians, trees, infrastructures, etc. An obstacle is considered as dynamic if it is moving. A point is considered as dynamic if it corresponds to a dynamic obstacle. The objective of the proposed approach is to classify each individual point of a PC as dynamic or not. Fig. 1 gives an overview of the approach. It is composed of five steps listed from $F1$ to $F5$.

Step F1: a point within a PC is characterized by its 3D (x, y, z) Cartesian coordinates. Let Γ_t designate the PC at iteration t and Γ_{t-K} the PC at iteration $t-K$ where K is a constant positive integer. A point $\gamma^t \in \Gamma_t$ is considered as *inconsistent* if $\{\gamma_{t-K} \in \Gamma_{t-K} : \text{dist}(\gamma_t, \gamma_{t-K}) < d\} = \emptyset$. The function dist represents the Cartesian distance between two points, and d is a positive parameter with a unit in meter (m). Step F1 generates the set Γ_t^I of all inconsistent points from Γ_t . In practice, Γ_t^I includes most of the dynamic points, but it may still include both some ground points and some static points as illustrated on Fig. 1-b.

Step F2: step F2 removes the ground points that may remain in Γ_t^I . We apply the ground segmentation approach proposed by Shen et al. [16] for this purpose. Step F2 generates the set Γ_t^{\prime} of inconsistent non-ground points as illustrated on Fig. 1-c.

Step F3: step F3 projects the points within Γ_t^{\prime} onto a 2D BEV grid as illustrated on Fig. 1-d. We chose a grid resolution of $r = 10 \text{ cm}$ in our example. This step generates the Boolean *Inconsistency Grid* (IG_t) at iteration t . For a cell A , $IG_t(A) = \text{true}$ if at least one point of Γ_t^{\prime} is projected within cell A . The cell is considered as *inconsistent* in this case.

Step F4: in practice, most of the inconsistent cells correspond to dynamic obstacles. However, some inconsistent cells may still correspond to non-dynamic obstacles or to the ground due to the imperfection of the ground segmentation function (see Fig. 1-c.). Step F4 aims to identify the dynamic cells among the inconsistent cells of the BEV grid. We introduce the notion of *Motion Area* (MA) for this purpose.

Given a cell A of the BEV grid, the MA of cell A designates the square region around A as depicted on Fig. 2. If W_{MA}

Fig. 2. Motion Area (MA) of a cell A subdivided into 16 zones

denotes the width of the MA, the latter will be composed of $W_{MA} \times W_{MA}$ number of cells. The Motion Area is thereafter subdivided into N_z number of *Zones*. For instance, the MA on Fig. 2 has a width of $W_{MA} = 9$ cells and is composed of $N_z = 16$ zones, numbered from 1 to 16.

The subdivision into zones can be configured in different ways. A simple method that we adopt is to first subdivide the MA into N_a number of angular sections. Each section is in turn subdivided into N_r number of sub-regions. The total number of zones becomes $N_z = N_a \times N_r$. On the example of Fig. 2, the MA has $N_a = 8$ angular sections indicated by 8 different colors and $N_r = 2$ sub-regions per section.

From the notion of zones, we introduce the notion of displacement. Let $\text{zone}(A, i)$ denote the set of cells that belong to the i -th zone of the MA of cell A . We consider that a *displacement* $d_{t,i}^A$ occurs if an obstacle has moved from one of the cells of $\text{zone}(A, i)$ at iteration $t-1$ and gets into cell A at iteration t . Since there is no direct measure of the occurrences of displacements, we estimate the occurrences of displacements in a probabilistic way.

We consider the couple $z_t = (IG_{t-1}, IG_t)$ of IGs at iterations $t-1$ and t as a pseudo measure of displacements and compute the probability of the occurrence of displacement $d_{t,i}^A$ given z_t as follows: $P(d_{t,i}^A | z_t) \doteq$

$$\begin{cases} \beta & \text{if } IG_t(A) = \text{True} \wedge \exists B \in \\ & \text{Zone}(A, i) \text{ s.t. } IG_{t-1}(B) = \text{True} \\ 1/2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where β designate a number between $1/2$ and 1 . Then, we derive the probability of $d_{t,i}^A$ given the history $z_{1:t}$ of all pseudo measurements from iteration 1 to t by applying the principle of Binary Bayes Filter (BBF) explained in [17]:

$$P(d_{t,i}^A | z_{1:t}) = \eta P(d_{t,i}^A | z_t) P(d_{t,i}^A | z_{1:t-1}) \quad (1)$$

where η is a coefficient of normalisation. To compute the term $P(d_{t,i}^A | z_{1:t-1})$, let A' designate a cell of $\text{Zone}(A, i)$ such that

$$P(d_{t-1,i}^{A'} | z_{1:t-1}) = \max_{\forall B \in \text{Zone}(A, i)} P(d_{t-1,i}^B | z_{1:t-1}) \quad (2)$$

We derive $P(d_{t,i}^A | z_{1:t-1})$ from the principle of BBF [17]:

$$P(d_{t,i}^A | z_{1:t-1}) = \zeta \cdot P(d_{t-1,i}^{A'} | z_{1:t-1}) + [1 - \zeta] \cdot [1 - P(d_{t-1,i}^{A'} | z_{1:t-1})] \quad (3)$$

where ζ is a constant between $1/2$ and 1 , and $P(d_{t-1,i}^{A'} | z_{1:t-1})$ the displacement probability of A' computed at iteration $t-1$

1. Eq. 3 enables us to compute displacement probabilities in a recursive fashion. Displacement probabilities are initialized with $1/2$ at the beginning.

Step F5: in step 5, we consider a cell A as *dynamic* at iteration t if a zone i exists such that $P(d_{t,i}^A | z_{1:t}) \geq P_{dyn}$. The threshold P_{dyn} has a value between $1/2$ and 1. Finally, points of Γ_t^i that were projected into dynamic cells are considered as *dynamic points*, as shown on Fig. 1-f.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The overall algorithm has 8 parameters. We use the following parameters in the current implementation: $K = 10$, $r = 0.1$ m, $d = 0.2$ m, $W_{MA} = 65$, $N_a = 8$, $N_r = 4$, $\beta = 0.55$ and $\zeta = 0.95$.

A. Dataset and ground-truth generation

We tested the proposed approach on the R2-S2 release of the publicly available TUMTraf Intersection Dataset [14]. The dataset contains a 30 seconds sequence of scans from a LIDAR mounted on an intelligent road infrastructure monitoring the traffic at a busy intersection. The LIDAR scans are produced at a rate of 10 Hz. The dataset includes object level annotations in the form of 3D bounding boxes with tracking IDs. Each bounding box is characterized by the position of its center, an orientation and a size.

In order to compare our approach with other dynamic point detectors, we start by transforming the original LIDAR scans into enriched PCs by adding a Boolean movement label to each point. For this, we use the assumption that LIDAR points situated inside a bounding box that has moved by at least 10 cm between two scans correspond to dynamic objects. Finally, points are filtered to keep only those within a region of interest of $100 \text{ m} \times 100 \text{ m} \times 7 \text{ m}$ in front of the sensor. We thereafter use these enriched point clouds as ground-truth to evaluate the performance of our algorithm for detecting dynamic points. Each enriched scan contains more than 18000 points.

B. Detection performance

To evaluate the performance of the detection algorithm, we have tested different values of the detection threshold P_{dyn} , computed the True Positive Rate, the False Positive Rate and the Jaccard index or intersection-over-union (mIoU) [18] over both dynamic and non-dynamic points for each value of P_{dyn} , and finally generated the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve on Fig. 3. The best mIoU score is 69.1% which corresponds to a True Positive Rate of 77% and a False Positive Rate of 0.22% (see Fig. 3).

The metric of mIoU is the reference metric used for comparing the performance of the state of the art dynamic points detectors in the Moving Object Segmentation (MOS) task over the SemanticKitti dataset [19]–[21]. The mIoU of the best dynamic point detectors lay between 62.3% and 76.7% on the current SemanticKitti MOS leaderboard [19], making the mIoU of 69.1% of our detection algorithm consistent with respect to the state of the art scores. While the evaluated task is the same, this comparison is not perfect though as

Fig. 3. ROC curve of the proposed method evaluated on the TUMTraf Intersection Dataset. The

both the dataset and the context are different. Indeed, unlike the TUMTraf Intersection dataset, the SemanticKitti dataset is recorded on a moving car equipped with a LIDAR. However, this comparison is useful for gaining an understanding of best-in-class performance, here of deep neural-network approaches which all require GPUs to run in real-time [1], [3], [11]–[13].

C. Execution time on embedded ARM CPU

We implemented the proposed approach in C++ in a Robot Operating System (ROS) environment. The program is executed on a Raspberry Pi 4 Model B equipped with an ARM Cortex A9 CPU and 4GB of memory. Table I shows the average execution time of each step of the proposed approach. The overall execution time is 75.04 ms on average. This represents 75% of the sensor's rotation period, which shows that the current implementation can reach real-time performance while running on an low-power embedded CPU.

Step	Step Name	Exec. Time (ms)
F1	Points inconsistency	20.04
F2	Ground segmentation	27.6
F3	BEV projection	1
F4	Dynamic cell estimation	21.4
F5	Dynamic points extraction	5
Total Exec. Time		75.04 ms (75% of sensor's period)

TABLE I
EXECUTION TIME ON AN ARM CORTEX A9 CPU (RASPBERRY PI 4)

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we present a lightweight approach for detecting the dynamic points within the point clouds produced by a LIDAR device mounted on an intelligent road infrastructure. The approach was evaluated based on a publicly available real-world dataset. The detection performance reaches a mIoU score of 69.1% while the average execution time on an embedded CPU occupies $\times 0.75$ of the period of production of the LIDAR scans, supporting real-time execution. Deeper exploration of the algorithmic parameters will be conducted in the future to analyze the impact of the parameters both on the detection performance and the execution time. Additional tests on larger and various datasets will also be realized for a wider evaluation of the algorithm on different scenarios.

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